

INTEGRATED ENVIRONMENTAL AND ECONOMIC ASSESSMENT OF RENEWABLE ENERGY PROJECTS BASED ON THE LCA-NPV-ESG APPROACH

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Abstract. *Traditional methods for evaluating renewable energy projects (LCOE and NPV) insufficiently consider environmental costs and ESG factors. This necessitates the development of integrated models that provide a comprehensive assessment of energy project performance. The objective of this study is to develop and test an integrated environmental-economic model based on LCA, investment analysis, and an ESG approach. The scientific novelty lies in the proposal of an environmentally adjusted NPV_{eco} indicator and an integrated efficiency criterion, K_{eff} . The model was tested using examples of 10 MW solar and wind power plants. The results showed that a project with the lowest LCOE does not always have the highest overall efficiency. The proposed tools help improve the validity of investment decisions in the context of the energy transition.*

Keywords: *renewable energy, life cycle analysis (LCA), ESG, net present value (NPV), levelized cost of electricity (LCOE), integrated efficiency, sustainable development.*

JEL Classification: Q42, Q51, G31, O13, L94

Introduction. The global energy transition and increasingly stringent requirements for sustainable development necessitate a shift from traditional indicators of the performance of renewable energy projects (RES) to integrated models [1,2,7,16,17] that take into account economic, environmental and social factors [2,3,16,17]. Despite the reduction in the cost of RES technologies and competitiveness in terms of LCOE [10,18], existing approaches do not fully reflect the hidden environmental costs at all stages of the life cycle and ESG risks [4,5,20]. A methodological gap is noted in the scientific literature: LCA and EIA methods are used predominantly in isolation from investment analysis (NPV, IRR, LCOE) [4,9,20], and ESG factors are often considered qualitatively [11,19,22]. Integrated quantitative models that allow the aggregation of heterogeneous parameters into a single performance criterion are lacking [5,21]. The aim of the study is to develop and test an integrated ecological-economic model for evaluating renewable energy projects based on a combination of LCA, investment analysis and the ESG approach [6,12]. The scientific novelty lies in: proposing an environmentally adjusted **NPV indicator** $NPV_{eco} = NPV - C_{env}$; developing an integral efficiency criterion $K_{eff} = \alpha NPV_{norm} + \beta (1/LCOE)_{norm} + \gamma (1 - Reco)$; justifying the procedure for normalizing different-sized indicators and adapting weighting coefficients within the ESG framework.

The methodological basis consists of: environmental impact assessment (EIA) [6-8]; life cycle analysis (LCA) according to ISO 14040 standards [12]; investment analysis (NPV, IRR, LCOE) [2]; ESG approach [5,21]. Environmental costs C_{env} are determined based on the results of LCA (equipment production, operation, disposal). Economic assessment is carried out using discounted cash flows.

Key formulas:

$LCOE = [\sum (I_t + O_t) / (1 + r)^t] / [\sum E_t / (1 + r)^t]$, where I_t is the investment costs, O_t is the operating costs, E_t is the production volume, r is the discount rate, t is the period.

$NPV = \sum CF_t / (1 + r)^t - CAPEX$, where CF_t is the net cash flow.

Eco-adjusted indicator:

$NPV_{eco} = NPV - C_{env}$, where C_{env} is the reduced environmental costs (utilization, damage to biodiversity, etc.).

Integral performance criterion:

$K_{eff} = \alpha NPV_{norm} + \beta (1/LCOE)_{norm} + \gamma (1 - Reco)$, where α, β, γ are weighting coefficients ($\alpha + \beta + \gamma = 1$) determined within the ESG approach; $NPV_{norm} = NPV / NPV_{max}$; $(1/LCOE)_{norm}$ is the normalized inverse LCOE indicator (incentive criterion).

The model was tested on two alternative projects: a solar power plant (SPP) and a wind power plant (WPP), each with a capacity of 10 MW. The initial data is based on average industry indicators for 2023–2024.

Results. Comparative characteristics of capital and operating costs (Table 1) form the initial basis for a subsequent quantitative analysis of the efficiency of alternative renewable energy projects. The presented ranges of CAPEX, OPEX, and service life reflect typical industry parameters and allow for the calculation of integrated indicators for comparable conditions.

Table 1 – Comparative characteristics of capital and operating costs of renewable energy sources

Type of renewable energy	CAPEX (\$/kW)	OPEX (% of CAPEX/year)	Service life (years)
Solar energy	800–1200	1–2%	25
Wind energy	1200–1800	2–3%	20–25

Estimated values of key indicators for 10 MW projects (discount rate 8%, term 25 years).

Based on the specified parameters, key technical, economic, and environmental indicators were calculated for solar and wind power plant projects with a capacity of 10 MW (Table 2). The resulting NPV, LCOE, and environmental risk (Reco) values demonstrate differences in project performance based on individual criteria, but do not allow for a definitive choice in a multi-criteria environment.

Table 2 – Comparison of two alternative projects: solar and wind power plants

Indicator	Solar power plant (10 MW)	Wind power plant (10 MW)
NPV, million \$	4.0	3.2
LCOE, \$/ kWh	0.05	0.07
Environmental risk (Reco)	0.2	0.3
NPV_{eco} , million \$	3.75	2.85

In this regard, there is a need to bring different-sized indicators to a comparable form through a normalization procedure, which ensures correct aggregation into an integral criterion.

This procedure allowed us to obtain standardized indicator values for the analyzed projects. The energy efficiency indicator (inverse LCOE) was similarly normalized, allowing us to take into account its incentive nature.

Further aggregation of indicators is carried out within the framework of the integral performance criterion, taking into account weighting factors reflecting the priorities of the ESG approach.

Normalization of indicators: NPV_{norm} : SES = 1.0; WES = 0.8; $(1/LCOE)$: SES = 20; WES ≈ 14.3. With weights $\alpha = 0.4$ (economics), $\beta = 0.4$ (energy efficiency), $\gamma = 0.2$ (ecology):

$K_{eff}(SES) = 0.4 \cdot 1 + 0.4 \cdot 20 + 0.2 \cdot (1 - 0.2) = 8.56$ $K_{eff}(\text{wind power plant}) = 0.4 \cdot 0.8 + 0.4 \cdot 14.3 + 0.2 \cdot (1 - 0.3) = 6.18$

The use of linear normalization is due to its interpretability and applicability to a limited sample size of alternatives.

At the same time, modern scientific studies emphasize that minimizing LCOE does not guarantee a project's environmental sustainability. In this regard, the role of integrated approaches combining economic and environmental criteria, including ESG parameters, is increasing [13,7]. The use of such approaches allows for the consideration of hidden costs and the formation of more sustainable investment decisions [6]. To test the robustness of the model, a sensitivity analysis was conducted (Table 3).

Table 3 – Impact of factors on NPV

Parameter	Change	Impact on NPV
Decrease in production	-10%	-25%
CAPEX growth	+10%	-15%
Tariff increase	+10%	+30%
Increase in the discount rate	+2%	-20%

The results of the sensitivity analysis showed that the greatest impact on NPV was due to changes in the volume of electricity generation (–10% generation → –25% NPV).

A comparison of environmental and economic factors reveals that low-LCOE projects do not always minimize environmental damage; the use of LCA allows for the consideration of hidden environmental costs; and the optimal solution is achieved through a comprehensive assessment. The addition of quantitative methods (NPV, IRR, LCOE) and environmental assessment tools (EIA, LCA) allows for: improved decision-making accuracy; reduced investment and environmental risks; and the sustainability of renewable energy projects.

The results demonstrate that the selection of a renewable energy project depends significantly on the evaluation criteria used. Specifically, despite differences in NPV, LCOE, and environmental risk values, a final ranking of projects is only possible when they are integrated into a single indicator.

The use of a normalization procedure and subsequent aggregation revealed a sustainable advantage for the solar power plant based on the integral Keff criterion. Furthermore, it was found that the contribution of individual factors to the final result is heterogeneous: economic and energy parameters exert a dominant influence, while the environmental factor serves as a corrective factor.

Thus, the calculation results not only confirm the differences between the projects, but also form the basis for a more in-depth analysis of the efficiency structure, which requires interpretation from the standpoint of modern scientific approaches to multi-criteria assessment of energy systems.

Discussion. The results obtained allow us to draw a number of fundamentally important conclusions of theoretical and practical significance.

First, it is confirmed that using individual metrics (NPV or LCOE) as the sole criterion leads to a partially distorted assessment of the effectiveness of renewable energy projects. In particular, minimizing LCOE fails to account for environmental costs and investment risks, while NPV fails to reflect technological and energy efficiency. This is consistent with modern research highlighting the limitations of single-criteria approaches.

Secondly, the proposed integration of indicators within the Keff criterion bridges this methodological gap by combining disparate parameters into a single assessment system. A key element is the inclusion of an environmental component through the NPV_{eco} indicator, which ensures quantitative accounting of hidden environmental costs previously not integrated into investment analysis.

Third, an analysis of the integrated indicator's structure revealed that normalized economic and energy parameters have the greatest impact on the final assessment, while environmental risk serves as a constraint, preventing the selection of projects with potentially high negative impacts. This confirms the need for a balanced approach to ESG criteria.

Furthermore, the conducted sensitivity analysis demonstrates a high dependence of NPV on changes in electricity generation, highlighting the critical role of the resource base and technological reliability in the implementation of renewable energy projects. This result underscores the importance of accounting for uncertainty in further research.

From a theoretical perspective, the proposed model advances the integration of LCA and investment analysis, facilitating a transition from isolated methods to integrated ecological-economic models. In practical terms, it can be used to substantiate investment decisions, develop ESG-focused strategies, and shape energy policy.

However, the model has a number of limitations. The use of a linear aggregation form and fixed weighting coefficients simplifies interpretation but reduces accuracy under complex scenarios. Furthermore, the lack of consideration of stochastic factors limits the model's applicability under conditions of high uncertainty.

In this regard, promising areas for further research include the application of multi-criteria analysis methods (AHP, TOPSIS), the use of dynamic weights, and the introduction of stochastic modeling (in particular, the Monte Carlo method), which will improve the stability and adaptability of the proposed approach.

The modern concept of sustainable energy is emerging at the intersection of several scientific fields, driven by the high complexity of energy systems and the need to consider multiple factors. The interdisciplinary nature of sustainable energy is supported by contemporary research, which emphasizes the need to integrate knowledge from economics, ecology, energy, and digital technologies [6,14,15]. These findings demonstrate the need to consider renewable energy projects within a broader interdisciplinary approach.

The sustainable energy model represents an integration of key knowledge areas, enabling a comprehensive assessment of renewable energy projects. Table 4 presents an interdisciplinary sustainable energy model, reflecting the interrelationships between key scientific fields and their contribution to the development of an integrated criterion for the effectiveness of renewable energy projects.

Table 4 – Interdisciplinary model of sustainable energy

Discipline	Contribution to the model
Energy	energy generation and distribution technologies
Ecology	impact assessment (EIA, LCA)
Economy	investment analysis (NPV, LCOE, IRR)
IT and digitalization	modeling, smart grid, AI

Sustainable energy development is possible only with the synergy of these areas, which ensures a systematic approach to management decision-making. The model (Figure 1) demonstrates that: the economic block (NPV, LCOE) determines the investment attractiveness of projects; the environmental block (LCA, environmental risks) reflects the level of sustainability and minimization of negative environmental impacts; the energy block ensures technological feasibility; the digital block (IT) integrates data and optimizes processes in real time. The central element of the model is the integrated efficiency indicator (K_{eff}), which aggregates the results of all blocks and enables informed decision-making. Within the interdisciplinary model, NPV is interpreted as an economic subsystem, LCOE as an indicator of energy and technological efficiency, and Reco (or a similar environmental index) as an environmental subsystem.

Thus, the K_{eff} formula becomes a mathematical expression of an interdisciplinary model of sustainable energy, combining economic, environmental and technological aspects in a single integral criterion.

The proposed approach is fully aligned with the key priorities of the Erasmus + program: interdisciplinarity; sustainable development; integration of science and education; and practical applicability of results. Universities play a special role in implementing this model, serving as platforms for knowledge integration, training highly qualified personnel, and implementing research projects. Universities are becoming key participants in the development of sustainable energy systems, ensuring the synthesis of science, education, and innovation.

Figure 1 – Interdisciplinary model of sustainable energy with an integral efficiency criterion (K_{eff})

The proposed integrated criterion for assessing the effectiveness of renewable energy projects is simplified and intended primarily for the initial comparative assessment of alternative options. The simplification of the model (Figure 1) is due to the following assumptions: linear indicator aggregation; fixed criterion weighting coefficients (α, β, γ); the use of average environmental risk values; and the lack of consideration of stochastic factors (variability in energy generation, tariffs, cost of capital, etc.).

Despite these limitations, the model has significant advantages: it provides deep integration of economic (NPV, LCOE) and environmental (LCA) parameters; allows for an objective comparative analysis of alternative projects; and is simple and easy to apply in practical settings where initial data is limited.

The model demonstrates (Figure 1) that: the economic block (NPV, LCOE) determines the investment attractiveness of projects; the environmental block (LCA, Reco) reflects sustainability and impact minimization; the energy block ensures technological feasibility; and the digital block (IT) integrates data and ensures process optimization. The central element of the model is the

integrated efficiency indicator (Keff), which aggregates the results of all blocks and enables informed management decisions.

Within the framework of the interdisciplinary model it is interpreted as follows: NPV is the economic subsystem, LCOE is the energy and technological efficiency, and Reco is the environmental subsystem. Thus, the Keff formula is a mathematical reflection of the interdisciplinary sustainable energy model.

This positioning is consistent with the key priorities of Erasmus +: interdisciplinarity; sustainable development; integration of science and education; and practical applicability. Universities play a special role in implementing the interdisciplinary model, serving as platforms for knowledge integration, training, and the implementation of research projects. In this context, universities become key participants in the development of sustainable energy systems, ensuring the synthesis of science, education, and innovation [13].

The proposed integrated criterion for assessing the effectiveness of renewable energy projects is simplified and is intended for the initial comparative assessment of alternative options.

The simplification of the model (Figure 1) is due to the following assumptions: linear aggregation of indicators; fixed weights of criteria (α , β , γ); use of average values of environmental risk; lack of consideration of stochastic factors (changes in output, tariffs, cost of capital).

Despite these limitations, the model has a number of advantages: it integrates economic (NPV, LCOE) and environmental parameters; allows for a comparative analysis of alternative projects; and is easy to apply in practical settings where data are limited.

Conclusion. The study confirmed that traditional approaches to assessing the effectiveness of renewable energy projects, based primarily on LCOE and NPV indicators, have a limited ability to account for environmental costs and long-term environmental impacts. This is consistent with current scientific findings on the need to transition to multi-criteria models for assessing energy systems [19,20,22]. The developed integrated LCA–NPV–ESG model enables a shift from a cost-minimization paradigm to sustainability-oriented decision-making in the renewable energy sector. The proposed NPVeco and Keff indicators provide a comprehensive consideration of a project's economic, environmental, and technological parameters. The results of the pilot study confirm the feasibility of using a multi-criteria approach to assessing renewable energy projects.

The obtained results can be used in the formation of energy policy, the development of ESG-oriented investment strategies and decision-making in the context of the energy transition, especially in countries with emerging economies, including Kazakhstan.

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